

Source: Shiri, M., [Heravi, M.M.](#), Zadsirjan, V. et al. Highly regio- and diastereoselective synthesis of oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrazino[1,2-a]indoles, based on a post-Ugi condensation: joint experimental and computational study. J IRAN CHEM SOC 16, 1517–1526 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13738-019-01632-3>

Highly regio- and diastereoselective synthesis of oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrazino[1,2-a]indoles, based on a post-Ugi condensation: joint experimental and computational study

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Abstract

A novel series of oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrazino[1,2-a]indoles were synthesized via a two-step pathway. In the first step, Ugi-four-component condensation of 2-formylindole, amines, (E)-4-alkoxy-4-oxobut-2-enoic acids, and isocyanides gave the corresponding Ugi-adducts. This adduct underwent intramolecular hydroamination in the presence of K₂CO₃ in CH₃CN at room temperature to afford diastereoselective synthesis of a range of oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrazino[1,2-a]indoles. A comparison of experimentally observed CD and UV–visible spectra with the theoretical DFT calculated ECD spectra was used to predict the major diastereomer.

Keywords: 2-Formylindole, Cyclization, DFT, ECD spectra, Intramolecular hydroamination, Multicomponent reaction, Ugi reaction, α,β -Unsaturated acids